

SURVEY – UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ZURICH

"USE OF THE INTERNET AND INFORMATION SEEKING AMONG PATIENTS WITH CARDIAC ARRHYTHMIAS"

SECTION 1: ABOUT YOU

1.1. Age of respondent: _____

1.2. Gender of respondent: Female Male Prefer not to say

1.3. What is your highest level of education?

Less than compulsory school Compulsory school

Vocational training/apprenticeship University of Applied Sciences

High school diploma (Matura/A-level equivalent) University

1.4. What is your current occupation? (If retired, please indicate and specify your former occupation) _____

1.5. What type of health insurance do you have?

Basic (general) Semi-private Private

1.6. Do you regularly conduct research as part of your job or in your everyday life? (e.g., internet searches, journals, books)

Yes, daily (→ continue to 1.6.1)

Yes, occasionally (→ continue to 1.6.1)

No (→ continue to 1.7)

1.6.1. Where do you search for information? (Multiple answers possible)

Internet Journals Books/Scientific literature

1.7. Do you deal with medical or health-related topics in your professional or private life?

Yes No

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SECTION 2: INTERNET USE AND INFORMATION SEEKING

2.1. Which technological devices do you use? (Multiple answers possible)

- Desktop computer Laptop Tablet Mobile phone

2.2. Which of the devices listed in question 2.1 do you use most frequently?

- Desktop computer Laptop Tablet Mobile phone

2.3. Do you use technological tools such as health apps or internet-connected health devices?

- I use health apps
 I use internet-connected health devices
 No, I do not use any of these

2.4. Do you use the internet to access medical or health-related information?

- Yes (→ continue to 2.4.1 and 2.4.2)
 No (→ continue to 2.5)

2.4.1. Why do you use the internet to search for medical or health-related information?

(Multiple answers possible)

- It is easily accessible
 It provides quick and clear answers
 It is ideal as a starting point
 It offers a broad range of information
 Other: _____

2.4.2. How often do you use the internet to search for medical or health-related information?

- Daily Weekly (<7x/week) Monthly (<4x/month)

2.5. Do you use other sources of information besides the internet to obtain medical or health-related information? (e.g., TV programs, friends/family, physicians)

Yes (→ continue to 2.5.1–2.5.4)

No (→ continue to 2.6)

2.5.1. Which other sources of information do you use? (Multiple answers possible)

General practitioner/specialist Pharmacy Family/friends

Television Magazines Other: _____

2.5.2. Please briefly explain why you use these sources:

2.5.3. Do these information sources influence your understanding of your illness and your treatment choices?

Yes No

2.5.4. How would you compare these information sources with internet research regarding your arrhythmia?

The sources selected in 2.5.1 are equally valuable as internet research

The sources selected in 2.5.1 are more valuable to me than internet research

The sources selected in 2.5.1 are less valuable to me than internet research

I do not conduct internet research, so I cannot assess this

2.6. When you first noticed symptoms of your current arrhythmia (before diagnosis), did you search for your symptoms on the internet?

Yes (→ continue to 2.6.1–2.6.6)

No (→ continue to 2.6.7)

2.6.1. Which search engine(s) did you use?

2.6.2. Did you search for a specific website?

Yes No

If yes, which website(s)? _____

2.6.3. What keywords did you enter in the search engine? (Please list as many as you can) _____

2.6.4. What type of information format were you looking for? (Multiple answers possible)

Text Images Video

2.6.5. Which types of information were you interested in? (Multiple answers possible; please indicate priority using numbers)

Possible conditions

Possible causes

Treatment options

Prognosis

Potential complications of various treatment options

Costs of different treatment options

Physicians who might be suitable for treatment

Clinics that might be suitable for treatment

Other: _____

2.6.6. Did the information you found online lead you to... (Multiple answers possible)

- Visit your GP
- Go directly to the hospital
- Consult a (specific) specialist
- Speak with a specific person
- Choose a particular clinic
- Prefer a specific treatment
- Decide not to seek medical care
- Other: _____

2.6.7. Why did you not conduct an internet search at that time? (Only answer if you selected "No" in 2.6; multiple answers possible)

- Internet search was not available at the time
- I was not interested
- I immediately consulted a physician
- I was admitted to the hospital as an emergency
- The arrhythmia was discovered incidentally (during hospitalization or a health check)
- Other: _____

SECTION 3: PHYSICIANS AND INTERNET RESEARCH – A COMPARISON

3.1. How long have you had a diagnosed cardiac arrhythmia?

- Less than 1 year 1–5 years 5–10 years More than 10 years
- Not yet diagnosed

3.2. Who first diagnosed your arrhythmia?

- General practitioner Private practice specialist Hospital/clinic

3.3. Who has been most important to you regarding the diagnosis, treatment, and ongoing care?

- Physician Clinic Both physician and clinic equally

3.3.1. Did you make the choice indicated in 3.3 based on internet research?

- Yes No, I decided on my own

No, but it was recommended to me by: _____

3.4. At your first consultation regarding your arrhythmia, were you satisfied with the explanation of the condition and treatment options provided by the physician?

- Yes (→ continue to 3.5)
- I was unresponsive/unconscious (→ continue to 3.5)
- I have not yet received a diagnosis (→ continue to 3.5)
- No, I was dissatisfied with both explanations (→ continue to 3.4.1)
- I was satisfied with the explanation of the condition but dissatisfied with the information on treatment options (→ continue to 3.4.1)
- I was satisfied with the explanation of the treatment options but dissatisfied with the explanation of the condition (→ continue to 3.4.1)

3.4.1. Did you subsequently search for answers to your questions on the internet?

- Yes No

3.5. After being diagnosed with a cardiac arrhythmia, have you researched the condition and treatment options on the internet at any point up to now?

Yes (→ continue to 3.5.1–3.5.4.1)

No (→ continue to 3.5.5)

3.5.1. What motivated you to research online?

The condition The treatment

Both the condition and the treatment

3.5.2. Which search engine and keywords did you use?

3.5.3. Do you gather your information from multiple websites or primarily from a single one?

Multiple websites

A single website, namely: _____

3.5.4. Why do you now conduct internet research?

To stay up to date

To compare information with what the physician told me

To better understand what the physician explained

Out of curiosity

Other: _____

3.5.4.1. Regardless of your answer to 3.5.4, have you noticed any discrepancies between what you read online and what your physician told you?

- Yes No

3.5.5. Why have you not researched your condition online after diagnosis? (Only answer if you answered "No" to 3.5)

- I was not interested
- I did not want to feel uncertain
- My physician tells me everything I need to know
- No diagnosis has been confirmed yet
- Other: _____

3.6. Have your internet searches influenced your treatment choices in the past or might they influence future treatment decisions?

- Yes, they have influenced my previous treatment decisions
- Yes, they have and will continue to influence my treatment decisions
- No
- I have not conducted any internet research
- I plan to do research, but I don't know whether it will influence my decisions

3.7. Have you sought or are you planning to seek a second medical opinion regarding the diagnosis or treatment of your cardiac arrhythmia? (If you were referred by your GP/specialist, you may also answer "Yes")

- Yes, I have already sought a second opinion (→ continue to 3.7.1)
- I plan to seek one (→ continue to 3.7.1)
- No (→ continue to 3.8)
- No diagnosis has been confirmed yet (→ continue to 3.8)

3.7.1. Did your internet research influence the decision to seek a second opinion?

- Yes
- No
- No, but I was advised to do so by my general practitioner
- No, but I was advised by: _____

3.8. How helpful have your internet searches been compared to your physician consultations regarding your arrhythmia?

- Not helpful
- Slightly helpful
- Supportive of the physician consultation
- Helpful, equivalent to a physician consultation
- Very helpful, equivalent to or even better than a physician consultation
- The two are not really comparable
- I have not conducted any internet research

3.9. Regardless of your answer to 3.8, have your online searches caused you any uncertainty regarding your diagnosis, treatment, or the further management of your arrhythmia?

- Yes
- Yes, but my concerns were resolved during a consultation with my physician
- No
- No, I have not conducted any internet research

SECTION 4: GENERAL

4.1. How often have you researched your cardiac arrhythmia on the internet up until today?

- Never
- Less than 5 times
- 5–10 times
- 10–20 times
- More than 20 times

4.2. Approximately how many total hours have you spent researching your condition on the internet?

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR VALUABLE SUPPORT!

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